

The specific model parameters of the USV are as follows:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 5255 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 7276 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 40362 \end{bmatrix} \quad C(v) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -7276v \\ 0 & 0 & 5255u \\ 7276v & -5255u & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$D(v) = \begin{bmatrix} 179.1|u| & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 11084+7602|v| & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 105786.3+25803|r| \end{bmatrix}$$

The initial position and velocity information of four USVs are set as: $\eta_1 = [-15, -18, -5^\circ]^T$, $\eta_2 = [-15, -5, -10^\circ]^T$, $\eta_3 = [-2, -2, -20^\circ]^T$, $\eta_4 = [-18, 7, -15^\circ]^T$, $v_1 = v_2 = v_3 = v_4 = [0, 0, 0]^T$. The initial position and velocity information of target USV is set as: $\eta_0 = [0, 10, 0^\circ]^T$, $v_0 = [0.5\cos(0.01\pi t), 0.9, 0]^T$. During the cooperative encirclement process, only 1th USV and 2th USV can obtain the state information of the target USV, i.e., the observation matrix $B = \text{diag}(1, 1, 0)$. The external environment disturbances are simulated as: $\tau_w = 10[2\sin(t/20) + \sin(t/30); 3\sin(t/20); -\sin(t/20) + 3\sin(t/40)]^T$.

The parameters of the finite-time distributed double power target state observer as: $k_{\zeta_1} = 1$, $k_{\zeta_2} = 1$, $k_{v_1} = 1$, $k_{v_2} = 1$, $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 2$. The design parameters of the finite-time distributed autonomous cooperative encirclement guidance law as: $k_{i1} = 0.3$, $k_{\text{rep}} = 0.8$. The maximum communication distance as $r_{\text{comm}} = 20$. The minimum safe distance between underactuated USVs $r_{\text{col}} = 7$. The design parameters of super-twisting finite-time disturbance observer: $l_1 = 1$, $l_2 = 2$ and $l_3 = 1$. The control parameters of the trajectory tracking controller as: $\delta = 0.1$, $k_{i\alpha 1} = 0.1$, $k_{i\alpha 2} = 1$, $k_{iu1} = k_{ir1} = 7$, $k_{iu2} = k_{ir2} = 1$, $k_{i\zeta_u 1} = k_{i\zeta_r 1} = 5$, $k_{i\zeta_u 2} = k_{i\zeta_r 2} = 1$.

Figure. 3 Convex hull shapes of cooperative encirclement

Figure. 4 Cooperative encirclement process of underactuated USVs

Figure. 5 Distance between the underactuated USVs members

Figure. 6 Distance from the center of the surrounding area to the target USV

Figure. 7 Surge force of the underactuated USVs

Figure. 8 Torque of the underactuated USVs

Figure. 9 The position observation errors of the finite-time distributed double power target state observer

Fig. 10 The velocity observation errors of the finite-time distributed double power target state observer

Figure. 11 Disturbance observation error of the ST-FTDO

Figure. 12 Reduce the number of the underactuated USVs during the cooperative encirclement process

Figure. 13 Increase the number of the underactuated USVs during the cooperative encirclement process

